

STAGES OF MODELING THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article presents an organizational and structural model for solving the problem of developing creativity in primary school students in a specific sequence and covers in detail the stages of developing creativity in students (didactic foundations, theoretical foundations, foundations and practical aspects of pedagogical creativity).*

Keywords: *creative, modeling, simulation, didactic principles, theoretical principles, principles of pedagogical creativity.*

Introduction

It is known that since the first century of the third millennium, the development of pedagogical innovations based on innovative approaches to education and their implementation in practice have become increasingly important. Of course, such pedagogical innovations can be effectively implemented through creative approaches. In this regard, it is impossible to ignore the fact that intellectually capable individuals will grow up among young people who live with progressive thoughts and innovative ideas. Experience shows that such important attention should be paid from the very first stages of the continuous education system, and through this, we will create a foundation for preparing active participants in the Third Renaissance from among the young people who have received such education and upbringing. Therefore, we must begin to form students - young people as innovatively developed intellectually capable individuals.

In our ongoing research, we have set the goal of solving the problem of developing creativity in primary school students based on the modeling method and creative approach. The following is important about the importance of the modeling research method: "Modeling" is the process of creating an analogy of a thing (object, subject) and a phenomenon (processes) using some artificial language. In modeling, its organizational and structural model representation is of great importance in pedagogy and psychology. In this case, the researcher identifies a system based on the behavior of a particular system and, therefore, selects or constructs an analogue, transforming another system into a system with similar behavior. Such behavior leads to reasoning about the similarity of structures. From this source it can be seen that modeling in our research work requires the study of each component of the development of creativity in primary school students (didactic foundations of the development of creativity in students, theoretical foundations, foundations and practical aspects of creative pedagogy) using models, and in doing so, it is necessary to take into account the corresponding internal and external influences.

Such modeling is one of the main methods of pedagogical and psychological research, and therefore, it is possible to freely use the modeling research method in solving the problem of developing creativity in primary school students. Through this, we also aimed to scientifically substantiate our research work and optimize the research process. The reason for setting such a goal is that, firstly, the modeling method of scientific knowledge will have a universal character in solving the problem under consideration, secondly, it will be possible to choose a convenient

option depending on the research situation when implementing it, thirdly, it will create wide opportunities for using the research method called the systemic approach to solving the problem of developing creativity in primary school students, fourthly, it will be possible to simultaneously take into account internal and external influences related to the system under consideration, and fifthly, in it, the mental operations (actions) of inference (recalling previous knowledge), comprehension (understanding new information) and thinking (expressing and discussing new ideas and thoughts) will always be in working order. We present such a model in Figure 1.

As can be seen from the figure, the process of developing creativity in primary school students consists of a single multi-stage, multi-parameter dynamic system, which consists of interconnected subsystems (didactic foundations, theoretical foundations, foundations and practical aspects of developing creativity in students; digital educational technologies; pedagogical creativity and its methodological directions). Also, the system elements of this system consist of indicators (parameters) used in the development of a methodology for developing creativity in students, which are also interconnected. The main system in this process, that is, the system for developing creativity in primary school students based on digital technologies, and its subsystems and system elements, have functional tasks directed towards a single goal and are carried out in the following logical sequence (stage):

1. Didactic foundations for developing creativity in students. The results of our research in this area have become an important didactic foundation:

- components of teaching students analytical thinking;
- didactic foundations for teaching students to think creatively;
- organizational-structural model of teaching students to think creatively;
- "Communication field environment" methodology for teaching students to think creatively;

At this stage, a collection of reference information, didactic materials, and creative information on the listed components will be formed and a database will be created on them. These

are one of the important informational bases for the development of digital educational technologies for the development of creativity in primary school students.

2. Theoretical foundations of developing creativity in students . The main focus is on the following components:

- creative thinking. This mainly focuses on the aspects of the student that are different from traditional thinking.

- These are: speed and flexibility of thinking; the ability to create new ideas;
- not using a template;
- originality;
- initiative;
- tolerance of uncertainty;
- intelligence, etc.

Another important aspect of this stage is that through the materials of this stage, it will be possible to develop innovative methods for developing creativity in primary school students.

3. Fundamentals of creative pedagogy for developing creativity in students .

The materials in these components are used in the preparation of multimedia educational technologies and electronic educational and didactic materials based on them (pedagogical software, intellectual teaching systems, preparation of a "Didactic portfolio" for studying a subject (subject), electronic albums, electronic atlases, virtual stands, audio and video materials, digital videos). These materials are a solid didactic basis for developing creativity in primary school students.

Practical aspects of developing creativity in students . Naturally, in any research work, their practical aspects serve as a scientific and practical basis for ensuring the excellence of the research work. This research work, special attention is paid to the practical aspects of the developed organizational-structural model for primary school students. At this stage, the main issues are to compare the research results with the planned results and to determine and evaluate the effectiveness of creative activities in this area.

In this research work, the results are expressed in a specific sequence regarding the solution of the problem of developing creativity in primary school students. They can be one or more, depending on the nature of the problem posed. In this research, we will also determine the levels of creativity development in primary school students as "excellent", "good", "satisfactory" and "poor". Based on the results achieved in problem solving, we designed to conclude that the levels of creativity development in primary school students are as follows, depending on their assessment levels:

- **creatively developed student** . This includes excellent students;
- **creatively gifted learners** . This includes advanced learners;
- **a student who has learned to think creatively** . This includes students who have received mixed grades ("excellent", "good", "satisfactory");
- **a student who loses his/her creative inclination** . This includes students who have mastered subjects positively, but have lost their initiative and curiosity for research.

These findings will be used to develop criteria for determining and assessing the development of creativity in primary school students.

Conclusion

The organizational-structural model of solving the problem of developing creativity in primary school students in this research work can guarantee one of the optimal options for research work in this direction. The reason for this is that it has an organizational-structural methodological character, developed to find a solution to the problem of developing creativity in students. By adapting its four stages of developing creativity in students (didactic foundations, theoretical foundations, foundations of pedagogical creativity and practical aspects) to the solution of the problem under consideration, it will be possible to develop other innovative methodologies for working on improving the intellectual potential of students - young people.

Recommendation. The process of formulating recommendations is carried out in the following sequence: “results achieved - conclusions - recommendations”. They can be found in the following forms:

The student is able to further develop creativity and is encouraged to continue research in this area;

The student has developed sufficient creative abilities and is recommended to be included in the ranks of creatively developed students;

the student is able to think creatively and is recommended to join the ranks of students with creative abilities;

The student is indifferent to the news and is encouraged to pay attention to the news around us and learn what processes are behind them, that is, it reveals the motivational process for creativity in the student and arouses interest in him.

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